

ADAPTATION OF A MACHINE LEARNING ASSISTED FAILURE PREDICTION METHODOLOGY TO BOLTED COMPOSITE JOINTS

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Machine learning for preliminary design of composite structures

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Use of machine learning for composite modelling [Yang et al, 2020], [Sun et al, 2021], [Logarzo et al, 2021], [Ostergaard et al, 2011]

Machine learning for preliminary design of composite structures

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Use of machine learning for composite modelling [Yang et al, 2020],
[Sun et al, 2021], [Logarzo et al, 2021], [Ostergaard et al, 2011]

Machine learning for preliminary design of composite structures

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Machine learning for preliminary design of composite structures

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The proposed preliminary design process
[Azeem and Iannucci, 2022]

Adapting proof of concept to bolted joints

CONTEXT . . . | METHOD | RESULTS . . . | CONCLUSIONS . .

Methodology for ML-assisted stress prediction, based on linear superposition [Azeem and Iannucci, 2022]

Stress component predictions using developed methodology [Azeem and Iannucci, 2022]

Demonstrated the use of machine learning to predict ply-by-ply stress variation at satisfactory accuracy, with reasonable amount of training data

Adapting proof of concept to bolted joints

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Adapting proof of concept to bolted joints

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Bolted Joint Bearing Failure

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Typical bearing mode bolted joint load-displacement behaviour

High fidelity model required to predict progressive damage

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Bolted Joint Bearing Failure

CONTEXT . . . | METHOD | RESULTS . . . | CONCLUSIONS . .

- ① STICK
- ② SLIP
- ③ STABLE FULL CONTACT
- ④ **DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT**
- ⑤ BEARING FAILURE ONSET
- ⑥ ULTIMATE BEARING FAILURE

Typical bearing mode bolted joint load-displacement behaviour

High fidelity model required to predict progressive damage

Bolted Joint Bearing Failure

CONTEXT . . . | METHOD | RESULTS . . . | CONCLUSIONS . .

Typical bearing mode bolted joint load-displacement behaviour (red-line indicating 2% offset)

High fidelity model required to predict progressive damage

Bolted Joint Bearing Failure

CONTEXT . . . | METHOD | RESULTS . . . | CONCLUSIONS . . .

Typical bearing mode bolted joint load-displacement behaviour (red-line indicating 2% offset)

High fidelity model required to predict progressive damage

Bolted joint bearing failure is a non-monotonic and complex process, requiring expensive models to predict accurately

Bolted Joint Bearing Failure

CONTEXT . . . | METHOD | RESULTS . . . | CONCLUSIONS . . .

Bearing bypass interaction curve
[Hypersizer, 2014],[J. Crews and R.Naik, 1986]

Characteristic length method [P.J. Gray and C.T. McCarthy, 2010],[Choi et al, 2018]

Methods used during the preliminary design of airframes predict stresses with FEA but require knowledge of failure loads and/or characteristic distances.

Bolted Joint Bearing Failure

CONTEXT . . . | METHOD | RESULTS . . . | CONCLUSIONS . .

Use a validated progressive damage model to predict failure load

Use a linear-elastic model to predict characteristic distance...

Methods used during the preliminary design of airframes require knowledge of failure loads and/or characteristic distances.

Bolted Joint Bearing Failure

CONTEXT . . . | METHOD | RESULTS . . . | CONCLUSIONS . . .

Predict failure load with machine learning (-> coming soon)

Predict characteristic distance/ stresses at failure with machine learning

Machine learning could be used to reduce experimental campaign or expert-dependant high-fidelity modelling.

Objectives

CONTEXT . . . | METHOD | RESULTS . . . | CONCLUSIONS . . .

Linear frictionless model
to train ML for stress
prediction

Friction(less?) model to train ML
for characteristic distance
prediction

- How does stress development change with varying friction/preload?
- How does failure stresses/characteristic distance change with varying friction/preload?
 - How does failure load change with varying friction and preload?
- Exploring volume averaged stress criterion [stress state, effect of preload, characteristic distance]

How can we adapt our methodology to predict stresses and stress at failure for bolted joints?

Methodology

CONTEXT ··· | METHOD | RESULTS ··· | CONCLUSIONS ··

Fully torqued = 10 Nm
Finger tight = 0.5 Nm

$$\bar{\sigma}_{V,i} = \frac{\sum_{element=1}^n \sigma_i * V_i}{\sum_{element=1}^n V_i}, \text{ for } i \text{ in } \{11,22,33,12,13,23\}$$

-> Hashin based failure criteria

Effect of preload on bearing strength

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Effect of preload on bearing strength

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Is the increase in bearing strength a result of the reduction in bearing stress due to friction or also the increased lateral restraint due to preload?

Effect of preload on bearing strength

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Effect of preload on bearing strength

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Experimental results indicate stick region plays primary role in increasing bearing strength

Effect of preload on bearing strength

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Effect of preload on bearing strength

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FEA results indicate preload has an adverse effect on joint damage after first ply failure and therefore a reduction in 'additional' bearing strength.

Effect of preload on bearing stress

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Effect of preload on bearing stress

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Compressive stresses ahead of hole boundary depend on total displacement, and compressive stresses at hole boundary depend on relative displacement.

Volume averaged stresses criterion

CONTEXT . . . | METHOD | RESULTS . . . | CONCLUSIONS . .

Volume averaged stress criterion

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Volume averaging over the bearing quadrant results in higher magnitude indices

Summary

CONTEXT | METHOD | RESULTS . . . | CONCLUSIONS . .

Effect of preload/friction on stresses

Effect of preload on bearing strength

VASC quadrant-based

Next steps

CONTEXT | METHOD | RESULTS | CONCLUSIONS . .

Effect of preload/friction on stresses

- Test for different bolted joint configurations
- Vary by-pass loading
- Check effect on tensile plane stresses
- Validate with analytical solutions

Effect of preload on bearing strength

- Improve FE correlation with experimental results and convergence
- Further experimental data
- Try different failure models

VASC quadrant-based

- Evaluate at larger distances from hole boundary
- Compare with PSC/ASC predictions, at various bypass loadings

References

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Thank you for listening!

Any questions?